

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/9000268>

Click evoked neurogenic vestibular potentials (NVESTEPs): A method of assessing the function of the vestibular system

Article in *Electromyography and clinical neurophysiology* · October 2003

Source: PubMed

CITATIONS

12

READS

55

9 authors, including:

Eleftherios S Papatasiou

Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics

83 PUBLICATIONS 380 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Marios Pantzaris

Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics

176 PUBLICATIONS 2,111 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Theodoros Kyriakides

Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics

104 PUBLICATIONS 1,921 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Sawas Papacostas

Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics

88 PUBLICATIONS 864 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Motion Analysis of the Carotid Artery [View project](#)

Linked 2 Safety [View project](#)

Click Evoked Neurogenic Vestibular Potentials (NVESTEPs): A Method of Assessing the Function of the Vestibular System

E. Papathanasiou¹, E. Zamba-Papanicolaou^{1,2}, M. Pantziaris², T. Kyriakides^{1,2}, S. Papacostas^{1,2}, P. Myrianthopoulou¹, C. Pattichis^{1,3}, I. Iliopoulos⁴, C. Piperidou⁴

Abstract

Objectives: To obtain neurogenic vestibular evoked potentials (NVESTEPs) with surface scalp recording using high intensity auditory clicks. The same stimulus is used in myogenic vestibular evoked potentials which has been shown to evoke potentials in the vestibular division of the vestibulocochlear nerve.

Methods: A whole head recording with surface EEG electrodes was performed using high intensity clicks in one normal volunteer to determine the best recording position for vestibular evoked potentials. The results were compared to responses at moderate click intensities used for brainstem auditory evoked potentials (BAEPs). The difference in the location of the two responses on the scalp was assumed to be from the vestibular system.

Results: Responses specific to the high intensity clicks were best obtained in the parietal areas, with no reproducible responses obtained in the same area with moderate intensity clicks normally used in BAEPs. Recordings in neurologically normal volunteers showed a consistent response with a negative polarity at around 3ms, which we therefore called N3. Two case studies are presented. The first case is a patient with unilateral sensorineural hearing loss with NVESTEPs present, suggesting that NVESTEPs is not a cochlear response. The second case is a patient with multiple sclerosis with demyelinating lesions in the pons and an unobtainable NVESTEP response.

Conclusion: NVESTEPs is a possible new diagnostic technique that may be specific for the vestibular pathway. It has potential use in patients with symptoms of dizziness, subclinical symptoms in multiple sclerosis, and in disorders specific for the vestibular nerve.

Key-Words: Vestibular – Evoked Potential – Click – Neurogenic – Brainstem.

Introduction

Neurogenic electrophysiological evoked responses from vestibular nerve stimulation in humans have

been attempted on numerous occasions in the past, using rotation (14, 15, 26, 27, 30, 46, 49, 51, 53) and head drop (30). Responses have been recorded at latencies of tens to hundreds of a millisecond. The diversity of responses obtained has been attributed to many of the studies using poor stimuli of low intensity, slow rise time and poor replicability (15). Myogenic vestibular evoked responses using high intensity clicks, recording mainly from the tonically activated sternocleidomastoid muscles, have recently been developed using a technique that can be easily performed in any neurophysiological laboratory that performs routine brainstem auditory evoked poten-

¹ Department of Clinical Neurophysiology.

² Department of Neurology, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, 6 International Airport Avenue, P.O.Box 23462, Nicosia 1683, Cyprus.

³ Department of Computer Science, University of Cyprus, 75 Kallipoleos St., P.O. Box 20537, Nicosia 1678, Cyprus.

⁴ Department of Neurology, Demokritio University Thrace, Ioakeim Kaviri 6, Alexandroupoli, Greece.

tials (BAEPs) (10, 11, 12, 13, 17, 18, 19, 23, 38, 39, 40, 43, 49, 58, 59). It is possible to use an auditory stimulus to test a vestibular pathway, that is, a pathway subserving posture and acceleration in movement, as it has been shown that saccular afferents are very sensitive to sound (12, 34, 37). This may be a consequence of the proximity of the saccule to the stapes footplate and eddy currents set up in the endolymph by sudden movement of the stapes (12, 56). The pathway tested is thought to be a disynaptic pathway descending from the lateral vestibular nucleus to the sternocleidomastoid muscle via the lateral vestibulospinal tract on the same side, arising initially from afferents of the saccule of the inner ear (10, 12, 24, 49). Using the same stimulus used in myogenic evoked responses, that is high intensity clicks, the initial objective of the present study was to investigate whether neurogenic electrophysiological activity specific for the vestibular system could be recorded from the cerebral cortex. In other words, can we record directly from a vestibular cortex, the existence of which, at least as a primary sensory cortex, is still being debated (5, 6, 16, 20, 21, 22, 33, 35, 44, 52, 55, 57)? We have shown a consistent waveform produced with high click intensity clicks from the parietal area, a response not present in the same area with moderate intensity clicks used in BAEP testing, with a mean latency of about 3ms. The latency of the response is suggestive of a brainstem origin and not in fact cortical as we had set out initially to record from, probably from or near the pons. Its presence during high intensity clicks and its absence during moderate intensity clicks in the parietal areas is probably suggestive of a vestibular origin. Two cases are presented that are suggestive of the nature of the above response. The first case is of a patient with unilateral sensorineural hearing loss with NVESTePs present, suggesting that the NVESTePs is not a cochlear response. The second case is one with multiple sclerosis with demyelinating lesions in the pons and an unobtainable NVESTeP response.

Materials and Methods

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Cyprus Institute of Neurology and Genetics and performed in the department of clinical neurophysiology.

Determining the best recording position for neurogenic click evoked vestibular potentials (NVESTePs)

A normal volunteer with no findings on neurological examination (male, age 27 years old) was tested to determine the best recording location on the scalp for click evoked neurogenic vestibular potentials (NVESTePs). A set of silver/silver chloride EEG electrodes was placed over the scalp according to the internationally used 10/20 system (29). All scalp electrode positions were referred to an electrode on the dorsum of the right hand. The scalp areas were cleaned with a skin preparation gel (Skinpure, Nihon Kohden Corporation, Japan) and applied using EEG paste (Elefix, Nihon Kohden Corporation, Japan). The subject was then placed supine on a bed with the eyes closed, relaxed but awake. The instrumentation used was the Nicolet Viking IV. Filter settings and sensitivity were the same as those used in BAEP recordings (bandpass of 100 Hz-3 kHz, 0.2 uV/division respectively) with a sweep of 1 ms/division. Oscilloscope readings were displayed with the negative polarity in the upward direction. The rate of stimulation was 10.1 Hz using a rarefaction stimulus delivered via headphones.

To differentiate the response obtained from the cochlear nerve pathway from that obtained from the vestibular pathway, two sets of recordings were obtained. The first set used a monoaural click intensity of 70 dB nHL, with a masking white noise intensity of 40 dB nHL for the contralateral ear, the click intensity used on most occasions for BAEP recordings. Only the left ear was tested. The results obtained were then compared to responses using a click intensity of 105 dB nHL (75 dB nHL masking noise for the contralateral ear), a high click intensity which is used to obtain myogenic vestibular evoked potentials. Again only the left ear was tested. Up to 1000 stimulations were averaged for each set. Because of the high click intensity used in the second set of recordings and the number of stimulations averaged was significantly more than that needed for myogenic vestibular responses (250 stimulations), caution was exercised to prevent patient discomfort. Two hundred and fifty stimulations at a time were given, with a one minute pause in-between. This method of stimulation was well tolerated. The difference between the location of the two responses on the scalp at

70 dB nHL and at 105 dB nHL was considered theoretically to be specific for the vestibular pathway. Only the left ear was tested in this particular volunteer, as we merely wanted to screen the best recording position for recorded NVESTEPS.

Normative values

After determining the best recording position and montage for recording NVESTEPS, we studied 13 neurologically normal volunteers (age range 16-34

years old, 7 male and 6 female). All subjects were instructed to have their eyes closed and to be relaxed but awake. In one subject, the eyes were kept open as he had the tendency to fall asleep. In this particular subject, recordings were also made after he was allowed to fall asleep. Recordings were then compared in this subject between wakefulness and sleep. Monoaural stimulation was performed separately for both left and right ears with a contralateral masking noise. Latency, amplitude and consistency of the results were recorded.

Results

Determining the best recording position for NVESTEPS

The responses obtained at 70 dB nHL and at 105 dB nHL are shown in Fig. 1. Reproducible responses of maximum amplitude are obtained in the central and parasagittal derivations at 70 dB nHL. This is expected as waves III, IV and V of the BAEP response are best recorded at the vertex (8). With a click intensity of 105 dB nHL, responses of highest amplitude were recorded in the parietal areas that were not present at all at 70 dB nHL in the same area of the scalp. In addition, it was noted that no responses were present in the frontopolar derivations. Based on the above, studies in the following normative population were performed using electrodes located at P3 and P4, both referenced to an electrode at Fpz, midway between Fp1 and Fp2. The subject stated that he felt no discomfort from the high click intensity together with the one minute pauses in-between.

Fig. 1. - Click evoked responses in a normal volunteer using a set of silver/silver chloride EEG electrodes placed over the scalp according to the internationally used 10/20 system. (A) Responses obtained with a click intensity of 70 dB nHL delivered to the left ear with 40 dB nHL white masking noise for the contralateral ear (70/40 dB nHL). (B) Responses obtained with a click intensity of 105 dB nHL delivered to the left ear with 75 dB nHL white masking noise for the contralateral ear.

Normative values

Monoaural stimulation was performed for both ears separately, at 105 dB nHL with a masking noise for the contralateral ear of 75 dB nHL, with bilateral recordings from P3 and P4. The number of waves obtained differed among the normal subjects, ranging from five negative waves in one subject (Fig. 2A) to one negative wave in three subjects (Fig. 2B). In all subjects, though, a wave of negative polarity that was located at around 3-3.5msecs was consistently

present. We therefore concentrated on obtaining normative data on this waveform. We have called this waveform N3 due to its predominantly negative polarity and its appearance at around 3 msec. This

Fig. 2. — Responses from two normal volunteers with a click intensity of 105 dB nHL to the left ear and 75 dB nHL contralateral masking noise showing in one neurologically normal volunteer a response with many waves present (A), whereas the second volunteer shows only one wave (B). The recordings are from P3 (top) and P4 (bottom) in each case. The consistent waveform in all normal volunteers is a wave at around 3msec, which we have termed N3.

wave is the most prominent of all the waves when more than one is present and of highest amplitude.

Normative values for the amplitude and latency of N3 at electrode locations P3 and P4 are summarized in Table 1. No significant difference was seen between the latency and amplitude of N3 obtained at P3 and P4 with either ipsilateral or contralateral stimulation.

The results were found to be affected by drowsiness and sleep (Fig. 3). The responses, even though present, were less organized and difficult to measure.

Case examples

The clinical utility of the above technique can be best illustrated by giving specific examples. The following cases were referred for electrodiagnostic studies.

Case I: History

SM was a 7 year old male with a past history of cerebellar tumor that was removed surgically 5 years previously, with the patient then receiving radiotherapy the following year. He was referred to us to rule out hearing loss as the patient was noted to not pay full attention at school.

Case I: Electrodiagnostic studies

Brainstem auditory evoked potentials were performed, which revealed an unobtainable reproducible BAEP response at 90 dB nHL (60 dB nHL masking noise for the contralateral ear) for the left ear (Fig. 4). However, one can see at the latency of 4.36 msec a reproducible wave, which we have labelled N3 in the figure. The right ear showed a response with normal absolute and interpeak latencies at 70 dB nHL (40 dB nHL masking noise for the contralateral ear) with reproducible responses obtained at click intensities as low as 30 dB nHL. NVESTEPs performed for the left ear though at 105 dB nHL (75 dB nHL masking noise for the contralateral ear) revealed intact responses again at 4.36 msec. Both the responses obtained at 105 dB nHL in the parietal area and at 90/60 dB nHL in the central area are the same wave.

Table 1. - Normative values for the N3 potential of the NVESTeP response

Parameter	Mean	SD	Normal limits ¹
(a) Absolute peak latency values			
P3 with left ear stimulation	3.42ms	0.27ms	<4.2ms
P3 with right ear stimulation	3.37ms	0.23ms	<4.1ms
P4 with left ear stimulation	3.24ms	0.25ms	<4.0ms
P4 with right ear stimulation	3.49ms	0.29ms	<4.4ms
(b) Amplitude values (onset to peak)			
P3 with left ear stimulation	0.43uV	0.19uV	0.13uV - 0.80uV
P3 with right ear stimulation	0.34uV	0.17uV	0.03uV - 0.75uV
P4 with left ear stimulation	0.30uV	0.16uV	0.05uV - 0.65uV
P4 with right ear stimulation	0.32uV	0.12uV	0.15uV - 0.48uV
(c) Latency interparietal difference (latency at P3 minus latency at P4)			
Left ear stimulation	0.18ms	0.16ms	-0.31ms - 0.67ms
Right ear stimulation	-0.11ms	0.15ms	-0.57ms - 0.34ms
(d) Latency interside difference (left minus right)			
P3	0.04ms	0.18ms	-0.30ms - 0.26ms
P4	-0.25ms	0.26ms	-0.62ms - 0.30ms
Ipsilateral	-0.07ms	0.22ms	-0.46ms - 0.42ms
Contralateral	-0.13ms	0.17ms	-0.47ms - 0.10ms
(e) Amplitude interparietal ratio (amplitude at P3/amplitude at P4)			
Left ear stimulation	1.59	0.64	1.0 - 3.32
Right ear stimulation	1.14	0.60	0.14 - 2.13
(f) Amplitude interside ratio (amplitude with left side stimulation/amplitude with right side stimulation)			
P3	1.57	1.10	0.67 - 5.0
P4	1.10	0.87	0.24 - 3.46
Ipsilateral	1.51	1.03	0.71 - 4.26
Contralateral	0.98	0.45	0.53 - 2.0

¹ For absolute latency the normal range is defined as the mean plus 3 standard deviations. For the interparietal and interside latency differences, the normal range is defined as the mean plus or minus 3 standard deviations. For amplitude and amplitude ratios, the range of values obtained (minimum to maximum) is used, as amplitude values are known to be skewed and not Normally (Gaussian) distributed (45, 46).

In the absence of a BAEP waveform, the NVESTeP response is also recorded at the vertex. We believe the presence of this waveform at 90 dB nHL is unique to this young age group, as preliminary data indicate a lower threshold of click intensity for obtaining NVESTeP in children (data not shown). We note also here that the latency of the N3 response (4.36 msec) is at the upper limit of normal. Our normative values of course do not at the moment include this patient's age. However, if we compare our results to what is known about BAEP responses in that adult values are reached by the age of two years of age (8), the above may be suggestive also of vestibular pathway involvement in this patient.

Case II: History

KE was a 33 year old male with a diagnosis of multiple sclerosis of the primary progressive type. An MRI of the brain (Fig. 5) showed evidence of several foci of high signal intensity on FLAIR and T2 weighted images involving the white matter of the periventricular areas and centrum semiovale and also the corpus callosum and brainstem. In the brainstem specifically, lesions were noted in the area of the pontine nuclei at the midpons level bilaterally, and also at the pons-midbrain junction on the right in the area of the corticospinal and corticopontine fibres.

Case II: Electrodiagnostic studies

All routine sensory evoked potentials performed were abnormal. Visual evoked potentials were unobtainable with left eye stimulation and prolonged with right eye stimulation (data not shown). Brainstem auditory evoked potentials showed prolonged III-V and I-V interpeak latencies with right ear stimulation and an absent wave V with left ear stimulation (Fig. 6C,D). Somatosensory evoked potentials revealed unobtainable cervical and cortical responses with bilateral median nerve stimulation and a prolonged cortical response with left tibial nerve stimulation (data not shown).

Fig. 3. – Responses from a neurologically normal volunteer during (A) wakefulness and (B) sleep. The responses during sleep are seen to be more poorly organized than during wakefulness.

Fig. 4. – NVESTEP (top) and BAEP (bottom) responses from a patient with left sensorineural hearing loss, obtained at 105 dB nHL and at 90 dB nHL respectively with contralateral masking noise. The BAEP response is unobtainable. However, an N3 response is still discernable. The NVESTEP response is shown at a different sweep and higher sensitivity. However, the N3 response in both cases is the same, occurring at 4.36msec. For the NVESTEP response, the sweep is 2 msec/division and the sensitivity is 0.1 uV/division, and for the BAEP response the sweep is 1 msec/division and the sensitivity is 0.2 uV/division (using the cross hairs on the right side of the figure).

Fig. 5. – T2 weighted MRI image of a patient with primary progressive multiple sclerosis, with demyelinating lesions seen in the pons.

Neurogenic vestibular evoked potentials (Fig 6A and 6B) revealed unobtainable reproducible evoked responses with right ear stimulation from both P3 and P4 with left and right ear stimulation. Left ear stimulation revealed however a slow reproducible response at 6.38 msec from P4. Figures 6C and 6D

Fig. 6. - NVESTEPs of the same patient depicted in figure 5 are noted to be unobtainable with right ear stimulation (B). Left ear stimulation produces a slow wave at 6.38 msec (A). (C) and (D) show the results of the patient's BAEP test, with waves I to IV obtained with left ear stimulation (C) and with interpeak latencies I-III and III-V prolonged with right ear stimulation (D).

show the BAEP responses for the corresponding ears. Wave V is absent with right ear stimulation, with the I-III and III-V interpeak latencies prolonged with left ear stimulation.

Discussion

This study has been able to record electrophysiologically a neurogenic signal from the scalp surface that we believe is possibly of vestibular origin. It is best recorded from the parietal areas and manifests as a negative polarity far-field potential occurring at around 3 msec after click stimulus onset. The

response, which we have termed N3 due to its predominantly negative polarity and that it appears at approximately 3 msec after stimulus onset, probably originates from the pons, and the examination requires the patient to be relaxed but awake.

That the above response is possibly vestibular in origin and not cochlear is shown by our first case study of a patient with unilateral sensorineural hearing loss, revealing intact NVESTEPs. This is similar to previous studies performed in deaf patients with high click intensities (31, 42). The former study observed a response at around 3 msec in 6.5% of subjects with profound hearing loss. This low percentage is probably due to the fact that they were recording from the vertex, the location where BAEPs are recorded from the scalp. However, we also recorded a NVESTEP response at the vertex in the absence of a BAEP response. But in this study we have shown that when a BAEP response is present in other cases, the vestibular response is best obtained in the parietal areas. One of their suggestions for the origin of this response was in the pons of the brainstem, as we have postulated.

We note in the first case also that the vestibular pathway may in fact be involved also, due to the perhaps longer latency than what is obtained in neurologically normal (albeit older) individuals. The cause of the unilateral hearing loss has not yet been determined. However, taking the past history of cerebellar tumor into account, one may hypothesize that the cause of the present problem was due to the tumor extending into the cerebellopontine angle, pressing on the eighth cranial nerve and causing nerve damage. In this case, the cochlear division seems to have suffered more damage than the vestibular division.

In the second case presented, demyelination was seen in the pons, in the area of the pontine nuclei. The almost complete absence of waveform with the neurogenic vestibular responses and their almost complete presence with BAEP testing suggests that the former is probably not of acoustic (cochlear) origin. Taking the responses with right ear stimulation as an example, waves I to IV is present with BAEP testing and are present five seconds after stimulus onset. If N3 was part of a BAEP response, we would have expected the former to be present as it appears at around 3 msec after stimulus onset.

With regards to BAEP recordings, wave III with a mean latency of 3.9ms is thought to originate from

the superior olivary complex in the pons of the brainstem (7, 9, 36, 54), although a part of wave III may originate from a medial nucleus of the trapezoid body (48). Click intensity does not affect sound velocity. However, the latency of BAEP waveforms is known to decrease by 0.03 msec/dB increase in stimulus intensity (8). Even so, a 35 dB nHL difference (between 70 dB nHL and 105 dB nHL) in click intensity would only cause a latency difference of 1 msec. Because the stimulus for both BAEP testing and neurogenic VESTEPs originates from headphones, the N3 response is therefore thought also to be a far-field potential that originates from or near to the pons. The second case study described above has lesions in the pons on MRI, which may have caused the abnormalities noted in his NVESTSTEP result.

The disorganization of the NVESTSTEP response with drowsiness and sleep is not surprising as it is known that the vestibular system has many connections with the reticular formation of the brainstem, one of the functions of which is in the control of the sleep-wake cycle (41). Projections exist from the vestibular nuclear complex to the reticular formation (4, 41). Input to the vestibular nuclear complex from the spinal cord in part also passes through the reticular formation (1). Both the reticular formation and the vestibular system, predominantly the lateral vestibular nuclei, are indispensable for normal posture, locomotion and the maintenance of balance (2). The association between the two systems has been suggested to contribute to sudden infant death syndrome (25).

We were not able to record a consistent response beyond 3 msec, at least within the sweep of 10 msec used in our study. In BAEP recordings, the average latency of wave VII, presumed to originate from the auditory radiations (9), is 9.2 msec. Future studies will need to use longer sweeps though to confirm the absence of a later response. The difficulty in obtaining a cortical vestibular response may be due to the fact that a primary vestibular cortex may not exist. The cerebral representation of signals received from the vestibular system is probably associated with inputs from both the visual and proprioceptive systems (5, 32). Because the vestibular system plays an important role in spatial orientation, perception of self-motion and object location, gaze and postural control, it has to collaborate intimately with

visual and somatosensory systems. This may be attributed to the fact that no pure unimodal vestibular stimulation occurs (e.g. during head motion or locomotion). Visual and somatosensory evoked potentials are easily recorded from the cerebral cortex probably due to the fact that they each have pure cortical representations.

A separate evoked potential test for the vestibular system is important to have. Usually in patients presenting with dizziness, BAEPs are requested to rule out brainstem and/or cranial nerve VIII involvement. The rationale for this is twofold. Firstly, the vestibular and auditory nerve for a significant part (or length) of their pathway pass very close to each other, and so it is expected that a lesion affecting the vestibular pathway may also affect the auditory pathway. Secondly, the brainstem is a small structure, and so it is expected that a lesion in this part of the brain would be big enough to affect the auditory pathway. However, most patients presenting with dizziness rarely report hearing problems, so it is therefore most likely that there are lesions that can specifically affect the vestibular pathway without affecting the auditory pathway. A close look at the anatomy of the pathway of these two sensory systems reveals that the auditory pathway takes on a predominantly lateral course rostrally through the brainstem, though it does cross to the contralateral side at several levels. Part of the vestibular pathway, on the other hand, especially those pathways that lead to certain parts of the thalamus and to the extraocular muscles (via the medial longitudinal fasciculus) pass medially through the brainstem (41). In addition, small infarcts in the cerebellum and the lateral medulla can present with ataxia and vertigo without other localizing symptoms (3). This is because some fibres from the vestibular nerve after entering the brainstem at the pons-medulla oblongata junction branch off before entering the vestibular nuclear complex and enter the cerebellum via the inferior cerebellar peduncle, an area not crossed by the auditory pathway (41). There have been numerous reports also of isolated attacks of vertigo being the initial and only symptom of vertebrobasilar insufficiency, sometimes a warning of impending stroke (28).

Further studies will involve obtaining normative values for NVESTSTEPs in other age groups, and also using longer sweeps. In addition, further studies are needed to assess our findings in different neurolog-

ical diseases, such as multiple sclerosis, as well as in otorhinolaryngological diseases, such as vestibular neuritis. The origin of the N3 potential should be further delineated with the help of MRI.

Conclusions

We have developed a neurogenic neurophysiological examination that possibly tests separately the vestibular pathway of the nervous system even in the presence of a BAEP response. This test would eventually prove useful in patients with symptoms of dizziness, as well as in detecting subclinical abnormalities in multiple sclerosis, and in diseases specific for the vestibular nerve.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to Ms. Elena Kyriakou, Ms. Elena Polycarpou and Ms. Christina Hadjiyianni for helping to prepare the figures.

References

1. ADAMS, D.R. and VICTOR, M.: *Principles of Neurology*, 4th edition, pp. 226-246, McGraw Hill, Inc., 1989.
2. APPENZELLER, O.: *The Autonomic Nervous System, An Introduction to Basic and Clinical Concepts*, 4th edition, pp. 257-283, Elsevier, 1990.
3. BALOH, R.W.: Episodic vertigo: central nervous system causes. *Curr. Opin. Neurol.*, 15: 17-21, 2002.
4. BERNE, R.M. and LEVY, M.N.: *Physiology*, 3rd edition, pp. 166-188, Mosby Year Book, 1993.
5. BRANDT, T. and DIETERICH, M.: The vestibular cortex: its locations, functions and disorders. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 871: 293-312, 1999.
6. BÜTTNER, U. and BUETTNER, U.W.: Parietal cortex area 2v neuronal activity in the alert monkey during natural vestibular and optokinetic stimulation. *Brain Res.*, 153: 392-397, 1978.
7. CHIAPPA, K.H.: Physiologic localization using evoked potentials: pattern shift visual, brainstem auditory and short latency somatosensory. In: Thompson, R.A. and Green, J.R. (Ed.), *New Perspectives in Cerebral Localization*, pp. 63-114, Raven Press, New York, 1982.
8. CHIAPPA, K.H.: Brain stem auditory evoked potentials: methodology. In: Chiappa, K.H. (Ed.), *Evoked Potentials in Clinical Medicine*, 3rd edition, pp. 157-198, Philadelphia, New York, Lippincott-Raven, 1997.
9. CHIAPPA, K.H. and HILL, R.A.: Brain stem auditory evoked potentials: interpretation. In: Chiappa, K.H. (Ed.), *Evoked Potentials in Clinical Medicine*, 3rd edition, 1997, Philadelphia, New York, Lippincott-Raven, pp. 199-249.
10. COLEBATCH, J.G. and HALMAGYI, G.M.: Vestibular evoked potentials in human neck muscles before and after unilateral vestibular deafferentation. *Neurology*, 42: 1635-1636, 1992.
11. COLEBATCH, J.G., HALMAGYI, G.M. and SKUSE, N.F.: Myogenic potentials generated by a click-evoked vestibulocollic reflex. *J. Neurol. Neurosurg. Psychiat.*, 57: 190-197, 1994.
12. COLEBATCH, J.G.: Vestibular evoked potentials. *Curr. Opin. Neurol.*, 14: 21-26, 2001.
13. DI LAZZARO, V., QUARTARONE, A., HIGUCHI, K. and ROTHWELL, J.C.: Short-latency trigemino-cervical reflexes in man. *Exp. Brain Res.*, 102: 474-482, 1995.
14. DURRANT, J.D. and FURMAN, J.M.R.: Long-latency rotational evoked potentials in subjects with and without bilateral vestibular loss. *Electroencephalogr. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 71: 251-256, 1988.
15. ELIDAN, J., LEIBNER, E., FREEMAN, S., SELA, M., NITZAN, M. and SOHMER, H.: Short and long latency vestibular evoked responses to acceleration in man. *Electroencephalogr. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 80: 140-145, 1991.
16. FAUGIER-GRIMAUD, S. and VENTRE, J.: Anatomic connections of inferior parietal cortex (area 7) with subcortical structures related to vestibulo-ocular function in a monkey (*macaca fascicularis*). *J. Comp. Neurol.*, 280: 1-14, 1989.
17. FERBER-VIART, C., DUBREUIL, C., DUCLAUX, R. and COLLET, L.: Réflexe sonomoteur vestibulaire dans les neurinomes de l'acoustique. *Rev. Laryngol. Otol. Rhinol.*, 116: 47-51, 1995.
18. FERBER-VIART, C., DUCLAUX, R., COLLEAUX, B. and DUBREUIL, C.: Myogenic vestibular-evoked potentials in normal subjects: a comparison between responses obtained from sternomastoid and trapezius muscles. *Acta. Otolaryngol. (Stockh.)*, 117: 472-481, 1997.
19. FERBER-VIART, C., DUBREUIL, C. and DUCLAUX, R.: Vestibular evoked myogenic potentials in humans: a review. *Acta. Otolaryngol. (Stockh.)*, 119: 6-15, 1999.
20. FREDRICKSON, J.M., SCHEID, P., FIGGE, U. and KORNHUBER, H.H.: Vestibular nerve projection to the cerebral cortex of the rhesus monkey. *Exp. Brain Res.*, 2: 318-327, 1966.
21. GRÜSSER, O.J., PAUSE, M. and SCHREITER, U.: Localization and responses of neurons in the parieto-insular vestibular cortex of the awake monkeys (*macaca fascicularis*). *J. Physiol.*, 430: 537-557, 1990.
22. GRÜSSER, O.J., PAUSE, M. and SCHREITER, U.: Vestibular neurons in the parieto-insular vestibular cortex of monkeys (*macaca fascicularis*): visual and neck receptor responses. *J. Physiol.*, 430: 559-583, 1990.
23. HALMAGYI, G.M., CURTHOYS, I.S. and COLEBATCH, J.G.: New tests of vestibular function. *Ballieres. Clin. Neurol.*, 3: 485-500, 1994.
24. HALMAGYI, G.M. and CURTHOYS, I.S.: Otolith function tests. In: Herdman, S.J. (Ed.), *Vestibular rehabilitation*, pp. 196-214, Philadelphia: FA Davis, 2000.
25. HARPER, R.M., WOO, M.A. and ALGER, J.R.: Visualization of sleep influences on cerebellar and brainstem cardiac and respiratory control mechanisms. *Brain Res. Bull.*, 53: 125-131, 2000.
26. HOFFERBERTH, B.: Evoked potentials to rotatory stimulation. Preliminary results. *Acta. Otolaryngol. (Stockh.)*, Suppl. 406: 134-136, 1984.

27. HOOD, J.D. and KAYAN, A.: Observations upon the evoked responses to natural vestibular stimulation. *Electroencephalogr. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 62: 266-276, 1985.
28. HOTSON, J.R. and BALOH, R.W.: Acute vestibular syndrome. *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 339: 680-685, 1998.
29. JASPER, H.H.: The ten-twenty electrode system of the international federation. *Electroencephalogr. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 10: 371-375, 1958.
30. KAST, R. and LANKFORD, J.E.: Otolithic evoked potentials: a new technique for vestibular studies. *Acta. Otolaryngol. (Stockh.)*, 102: 175-178, 1986.
31. KATO, T., SHIRAIISHI, K., EURA, Y., SHIBATA, K., SAKATA, T., MORIZONO, T. and SODA, T.: A "neural" response with 3-ms latency evoked by loud sound in profoundly deaf patients. *Audiol. Neurootol.*, 3: 253-264, 1998.
32. KLUGE, M., BEYENBURG, S., FERNANDEZ, G. and ELGER, C.E.: Epileptic vertigo: evidence for vestibular representation in human frontal cortex. *Neurology*, 55: 1906-1908, 2000.
33. KORNHUBER, H.H., FREDRICKSON, J.M. and FIGGE, U.: Die kortikale projection der vestibularen afferenz beim rhesusaffen. *Pflugers Arch.*, 283: 20-25, 1965.
34. MCCUE, M.P. and GUINAN, J.J.: Acoustically responsive fibers in the vestibular nerve of the cat. *J. Neurosci.*, 14: 6058-6070, 1994.
35. MICKLE, W.A. and ADES, H.W.: A composite sensory projections area in the cerebral cortex of cat. *Am. J. Physiol.*, 170: 682-689, 1952.
36. MOLLER, A.R. and JANNETTA, P.J.: Auditory evoked potentials recorded intracranially from the brainstem in man. *Exp. Neurol.*, 78: 144-157, 1982.
37. MUROFUSHI, T., CURTHOYS, I.S., TOPPLE, A.N., COLEBATCH, J.G. and HALMAGYI, G.M.: Responses of guinea pig primary vestibular neurons to clicks. *Exp. Brain Res.*, 103: 174-178, 1995.
38. MUROFUSHI, T., HALMAGYI, G.M., YAVOR, R.A. and COLEBATCH, J.G.: Absent vestibular evoked myogenic potentials in vestibular neurolabyrinthitis. *Arch. Otolaryngol. Head Neck Surg.*, 122: 845-848, 1996.
39. MUROFUSHI, T., MATSUZAKI, M. and MIZUNO, M.: Vestibular evoked myogenic potentials in patients with acoustic neuromas. *Arch. Otolaryngol. Head Neck Surg.*, 124: 509-512, 1998.
40. MUROFUSHI, T., SHIMUZU, K., TAKEGOSHI, H. and CHENG, P-W.: Diagnostic value of prolonged latencies in the vestibular evoked myogenic potential. *Arch. Otolaryngol. Head Neck Surg.*, 127: 1069-1072, 2001.
41. NOLTE, J.: *The Human Brain: An Introduction to its Functional Anatomy*, 3rd edition, Mosby Year Book, 1993.
42. OCHI, K. and OHASHI, T.: Sound-evoked myogenic potentials and responses with 3-ms latency in auditory brainstem response. *Laryngoscope*, 111: 1818-1821, 2001.
43. OCHI, K., OHASHI, T. and NISHINO, H.: Variance of vestibulo-evoked myogenic potentials. *Laryngoscope*, 111: 322-327, 2001.
44. ODKVIST, L.M., SCHWARZ, D.W., FREDRICKSON, J.M. and HASSLER, R.: Projection of the vestibular nerve to the area 3a arm field in the squirrel monkey (*saimiri sciureus*). *Exp. Brain Res.*, 21: 97-105, 1974.
45. OKEN, B.S.: Statistics for evoked potentials. In: Chiappa, K.H. (Ed.), *Evoked Potentials in Clinical Medicine*, 3rd edition, pp. 565-578, Philadelphia, New York, Lippincott-Raven, 1997.
46. PAPATHANASIOU, E.S., CLEANTHOUS, M.E.G. and PAPA-COSTAS, S.S.: Using statistics to determine the tolerance limits of normal values in evoked potential testing. *Am. J. END Technol.*, 38: 33-42, 1998.
47. PIRODDA, E., GHEDINI, S. and ZEMETI, M.A.: Investigations into vestibular evoked responses. *Acta. Otolaryngol. (Stockh.)*, 104: 77-84, 1987.
48. RICHTER, E.A., NORRIS, B.A., FULLERTON, B.A., LEVINE, R.A. and KIANG, NY-S.: Is there a medial nucleus of the trapezoid body in humans? *Am. J. Anat.*, 168: 157-166, 1983.
49. ROBERSON, D.D. and IRELAND, D.J.: Vestibular evoked myogenic potentials. *J. Otolaryngol.*, 24: 3-8, 1995.
50. SALAMY, J., POTVIN, A., JONES, K. and LANDRETH, J.: Cortical evoked responses to labyrinthine stimulation in man. *Psychophysiology*, 12: 55-61, 1975.
51. SCHNEIDER, D., SCHNEIDER, L., CLAUSSEN, C-F. and KOLCHEV C. Cortical representation of the vestibular system as evidenced by brain electrical activity mapping of vestibular late evoked potentials. *ENT-Ear, Nose & Throat Journal*, 80(4): 251-265, 2001.
52. SCHWARZ, D.W.F. and FREDRICKSON, J.M.: Rhesus monkey vestibular cortex: a bimodal primary projection field. *Science*, 172: 280-281, 1971.
53. SOHMER, H., ELIDAN, J., RODIONOV, V. and PLOTNIK, M.: Short and middle latency vestibular evoked potentials to angular and linear acceleration. *Electroencephalogr. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 50: 226-234, 1999.
54. STARR, A. and HAMILTON, A.E.: Correlation between confirmed sites of neurologic lesions and abnormalities of farfield auditory brainstem responses. *Electroencephalogr. Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 41: 595-608, 1976.
55. VIDAL, P.P., DE WAELE, C., BAUDONNIERE, P.M., LEPECQ, J.C. and BA HUY, P.T.: Vestibular projections in the human cortex. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 871: 455-457, 1999.
56. VON BÉKÉSY, G.: Uber akustische Reizung des Vestibularapparates. *Arch. Ges. Physiol.*, 236: 59-76, 1935.
57. WALZL, E.M. and MOUNTCASTLE, V.R.: Projections of the vestibular nerve to cerebral cortex of cat. *Am. J. Physiol.*, 159: 595-598, 1949.
58. WELGAMPOLA, M.S. and COLEBATCH, J.G.: Vestibulocollic reflexes: normal values and the effect of age. *Clin. Neurophysiol.*, 112: 1971-1979, 2001.
59. WU, C.H. and MUROFUSHI, T.: The effect of click repetition rate on vestibular evoked myogenic potential. *Acta. Otolaryngol.*, 119: 29-32, 1999.

Address reprint requests to:

Eleftherios S. Papathanasiou,
 Department of Clinical Neurophysiology,
 The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics,
 6 International Airport Avenue,
 P.O.Box 23462, Nicosia 1683, Cyprus.

Tel: +357-22-392712

Fax: +357-22-358238

E-mail: neurophy@cing.ac.cy